

New distribution record of soft ticks *Argas (persicargas) persicus* Oken from West Bengal, India

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Abstract

Knowledge regarding the tick species diversity and its geographical distribution in the Indian subcontinent, including West Bengal state is pretty scarce. Owing to its veterinary and medical importance, detailed morphological studies on tick species is the need of the hour. During a recent survey (2022) undertaken in West Bengal, 16 specimens of soft tick species *Argas (persicargas) persicus* Oken, 1818 (family Argasidae) from a feral pigeon (*Columba* spp.) were collected, identified and is being added to the fauna of the state for the first time. Discussion regarding its hosts, distribution, veterinary and medical importance is also provided. Hence knowledge regarding the diversity of tick species encountered on the wild as well as domestic fauna, along with that the probable pathogenic microorganisms that it can transmit as vectors could significantly contribute to Wildlife conservation efforts.

Keywords: *Acari, Ixodida, ticks, new record, vector.*

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Introduction

Ticks are infamous for being one of the most competent obligatory hematophagous ectoparasitic arachnids belonging to order Ixodida of subclass Acari. They are predominantly parasitizing on terrestrial and flying vertebrates, including humans (Hoogstraal, 1985; Jongejan and Uilenberg, 2004). Members of this group harbour diverse pathogenic microorganisms and transmit diseases across wide range of hosts and are one of the most potent vectors across the arthropod world (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2010). The order Ixodida is classified into three extant families, Ixodidae (hard ticks), Argasidae (soft ticks) and Nuttalliellidae (monotypic) (Keirans and Robbins, 1999; Estrada-Peña and Fuente 2018), and one extinct family Deincrotonidae (Peñalver *et al.*, 2017). This group is known by approximately 971 species, of these, 762 species belong to Ixodidae (hard ticks) (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2023), 208 species of Argasidae (soft ticks) (Nava *et al.*, 2017) and 1 species of Nuttalliellidae (*Nuttalliella namaqua*) across the globe, of which 106 species are reported

from India (Geevarghese *et al.*, 1997), including 32 species of hard ticks from West Bengal state (Sanyal and De, 2001).

During a recent survey (2022) in West Bengal, 16 specimens of *Argas (persicargas) persicus* Oken, 1818 (family Argasidae) from a feral pigeon (*Columba* spp.) were collected, identified and is being added to the fauna of the state for the first time. The life cycle of this species consists 9 stages; egg, larva, and five nymphal instars and adult (♂, ♀) (Zahid *et al.*, 2021). *Argas (persicargas) persicus* is known for causing spirochetosis in fowl (Burroughs, 1947) by transmitting *Borrelia anserina* (Chegeni *et al.*, 2017). They also feed on the host body and can cause significant physiological problems like weakness and anemia, reduction in egg production, growth and lead to paralysis (Burroughs, 1947).

Diagnostic features, distribution details, materials studied, and registration numbers as recorded for each specimen housed at Zoological survey of India in National Zoological Collection (NZC), Kolkata are also provided.

Plate 1: Figure 1-6, *Argas (persicargas) persicus*. 1. Male, dorsal; 2. Male, ventral; 3. Female, dorsal; 4. Female, ventral; 5. Nymph (1st instar), dorsal; 6. Nymph (1st instar), ventral.

Materials and Methods

Owing to their nidicolous behaviour, such endophilic ticks specimens were collected, manually from a feral pigeon as well as from its nests. The collected specimens were preserved in 70% alcohol. Photographs were taken by Nikon stereo zoom microscope (NIKON model SMZ25) using Nikon software

application suite (NIS-Elements BR 5.20.00 64-bit) and were edited by using Adobe Photoshop CS version 8.0.1. Specimens of this species were identified with help of published identification keys from (Furman and Loomis, 1984; Geevarghese and Mishra, 2011; Durden and Beati, 2013; Barros-Battesti *et al.*, 2013; Petney *et al.*, 2017).

Results

Family Argasidae

Argas (persicargas) persicus Oken, 1818

(Plate 1, Figs. 1-6)

Diagnosis: Idiosoma oval, longer than broad, narrow anteriorly and broad posteriorly; dorsal body surface dull greyish yellow, medially dark, marginally pale and translucent in unfed individuals; but in engorged individuals medially opaque, with leaden appearance; peripheral suture characterized by large rectangular or sub-rectangular cells; dorsum gradually flattened in unfed specimens, and medially thickened, idiosoma thins out peripherally to an acute margin, to some extent reflexed; entire idiosoma covered with leathery textured chitinous cuticle; discs scattered over the entire dorsum, but restricted ventrally to the marginal and posterior parts; marginal or peripheral cells of dorsum with only one large setiferous pit enclosing most of the surface area; anterior extremity of the ventral surface bears somewhat rectangular camerostome with capitulum guarded laterally by 2 camerostome folds; capitular margins straight; supracoxal folds start from coxa I with slight inward curve and run all along external margins of coxa IV, then diverge abruptly outward terminating near the lateral margins of the body; coxal folds start from the interspace of coxa I and II and run all along the sagittal margins of coxa I to III, diverge after coxa IV, terminating near the anterior margins of posterior third of idiosoma; small and oval spiracular plates exterior to the supracoxal folds in alignment with coxa IV; genital orifice in both sexes lie in the mid-ventral line in transverse alignment with the first coxal interspace; female genital orifice conspicuous with transverse slit and guarded by tumid lips; posterior lip protruded and overlapped the anterior lip with apertural opening directed towards the basis capitulum; male genital orifice small, strongly arched with crescentic slit; 1st nymphal instar devoid of genital aperture; anal groove absent in both sexes; gene's organ open externally in the lower part of camerostomal depression. (Robinson and Davidson, 1913; Walker *et al.*, 2003; Basu and Charles, 2017; Petney *et al.*, 2017).

Material examined: 6♂, 8♀, 2 Nymphs (1st Nymphal Instar), India: West Bengal, Kolkata,

(22° 34' 50.592" N, 88° 26' 49.632" E), Feral pigeons (*Columba* spp.), 04.vii.2022, Registration No: 6990/17.

Host: *Argas (persicargas) persicus* is reported previously from Pigeon (*Columba* spp.), sparrow (*Passer montanus*), swallow (*Hirundo* spp.), Domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) (Zahid *et al.*, 2021). This species is also reported from Indian Myna (*Acridotheres tristis*), Pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*) (Geevarghese *et al.*, 1997).

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chandigarh, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal (**new record**) (Geevarghese *et al.*, 1997).

Elsewhere: This is a widespread species, occurring in most of the hot and humid climatic regions across the world (Muñoz-Leal *et al.*, 2018).

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References

- Barros-Battesti, D.M., Ramirez, D.G., Landulfo, G.A., Faccini, J.L.H., Dantas-Torres, F., Labruna, M.B., Venzal, J.M. and Onofrio, V.C. 2013. Immature argasid ticks: diagnosis and keys for Neotropical region. *Revista Brasileira de Parasitologia Veterinária* 22: 443-456.
- Basu, A.K. and Charles, R.A. 2017. Ticks of Trinidad and Tobago- an Overview. Chapter 3- Tick species present in Trinidad and Tobago. London: Elsevier, 39-77.
- Burroughs, A.L. 1947. Fowl spirochetosis transmitted by *Argas persicus* (Oken), 1818 from Texas. *Science* 105(2735): 577-577.
- Chegeni, A.H., Telmadarraiy, Z., Tavakoli, M. and Faghihi, F. 2017. Molecular detection of *Borrelia anserina* in *Argas persicus*

- (Acari: Argasidae) ticks collected from Lorestan province, west of Iran. *Persian Journal of Acarology* 6(4): 287-297.
- Durden, L.A. and Beati, L. 2013. Modern tick systematics. *In*: D.E. Sonenshine and R.M. Roe (eds.) *Biology of ticks*. Volume 1. New York: Oxford University Press, 17-58.
- Estrada-Peña, A. and de la Fuente, J. 2018. The fossil record and the origin of ticks revisited. *Experimental and Applied Acarology* 75(2): 255-261.
- Furman, D.P. and Loomis, E.C. 1984. The Ticks of California (Acari: Ixodida), *Bulletin of California Insect Survey* Volume 25. California: University of California Press. 356 pp.
- Geevarghese, G. and Mishra, A.C. 2011. Introduction. *Haemaphysalis* ticks of India. Elsevier Insights. 260pp.
- Geevarghese, G., Fernandes, S. and Kulkarni, S.M. 1997. A checklist of Indian ticks (Acari: Ixodoidea). *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences* 67(5): 566-574.
- Guglielmone, A.A., Nava, S. and Robbins, R.G. 2023. Geographic distribution of the hard ticks (Acari: Ixodida: Ixodidae) of the world by countries and territories. *Zootaxa* 5251(1): 1-274.
- Guglielmone, A.A., Robbins, R.G., Apanaskevich, D.A., Petney, T.N., Estrada-Peña, A., Horak, I.G., Shao, R. and Barker, S.C. 2010. The Argasidae, Ixodidae and Nuttalliellidae (Acari: Ixodida) of the world: a list of valid species names. *Zootaxa* 2528: 1–28.
- Hoogstraal, H. 1985. Argasid and nuttalliellid ticks as parasites and vectors. *Advances in parasitology* 24: 135-238.
- Jongejan, F. and Uilenberg, G. 2004. The global importance of ticks. *Parasitology* 129(S1): S3-S14.
- Keirans, J.E. and Robbins, R.G. 1999. A world checklist of genera, subgenera, and species of ticks (Acari: Ixodida) published from 1973-1997. *Journal of Vector Ecology: Journal of the Society for Vector Ecology* 24(2): 115-129.
- Muñoz-Leal, S., Venzal, J.M., Nava, S., Reyes, M., Martins, T.F., Leite, R.C. Vilela, V.L.R., Benatti, H.R., Ríos-Rosas, D., Barros-Battesti, D.M., González-Acuña, D. and Labruna, M.B. 2018. The geographic distribution of *Argas (Percicargas) miniatus* and *Argas (Percicargas) persicus* (Acari: Argasidae) in America, with morphological and molecular diagnoses from Brazil, Chile and Cuba. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases* 9(1): 44-56.
- Nava, S., Venzal, J.M., Acuña, D.G., Martins, T.F. and Guglielmone, A.A. 2017. Ticks of the Southern Cone of America: diagnosis, distribution, and hosts with taxonomy, ecology and sanitary importance. Academic Press, Elsevier Inc. 348 pp.
- Peñalver, E., Arillo, A., Delclòs, X., Peris, D., Grimaldi, D.A., Anderson, S.R. Nascimbene, P.C. and Fuente, R.P. 2017. Ticks parasitised feathered dinosaurs as revealed by Cretaceous amber assemblages. *Nature Communications* 8(1): 1924.
- Petney, T.N., Pfäffle, M.P., Sprong, H., Mihalca, A.D. and Estrada-Peña, A. 2017. How to collect ticks and interpret these collections. *In*: A. Estrada-Peña, A. Mihalca, T. Petney (eds.) *Ticks of Europe and North Africa: A Guide to Species Identification*. Cham: Springer 5-10.
- Robinson, L. and Davidson, J. 1913. The Anatomy of *Argas persicus* (Oken 1818). *Parasitology* 6(3): 217-256.
- Sanyal, A.K. and De, S.K. 2001. Diversity in ticks (Acari) of West Bengal. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India* 99(1-4): 65-74.
- Walker, A.R., Bouattour, A., Camicas, J.L., Estrada-Peña, A., Horak, I.G., Latif, A.A., Pegram, R.G., and Preston, P.M. 2003. Species of Ticks. *In*: *Ticks of domestic animals in Africa: a guide to identification of species*. Edinburgh: Bioscience Reports: 67-70.
- Zahid, H., Muñoz-Leal, S., Khan, M.Q., Alouffi, A. S., Labruna, M.B., and Ali, A. 2021. Life cycle and genetic identification of *Argas persicus* infesting domestic fowl in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 8: 664731.